

Analysis of Emergency Medical Care system condition in developing countries on the Ghana's example

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Abstract

Emergency Medical Care is one of the most important systems ensuring security of citizens. Developing countries have limited financial resources wherefore financial outlay on Emergency Medical Care system is insufficient. In 2015 Ghana had only 128 ambulances. Only 59.4% of the areas were accessible to the ambulance in 60 minutes, and after analyzing the location of the rescue station, only 79% of the population had access to the ambulance in 60 minutes. Lack of basic medical equipment, low educational level ambulance service employees and long distances between hospitals cause that quality of medical assistance is frequently low and limited to transport services. Ghana National Ambulance Service created 12-months training programme for their employees however, private organizations do not have mandatory requirements for the training of employees. The lack of regulations on Emergency Medical Care makes some of the medical rescue workers even less knowledgeable about medical emergencies, which reduces the quality of health services provided to the public. The analysis of the epidemiological situation and the statistics on resources and the condition of Emergency Medical Care system in Ghana indicates that increasing public awareness of first aid and the qualification of medical workers could increase the survivability of victims of traffic accidents in pre-hospital care.

Key words: *Emergency Medical Care, Ghana, developing countries*

Introduction

Emergency Medical Care is one of the most important systems ensuring security of citizens. The system provides emergency assistance to save health and human life in the event of an accident or illness. However, there are places on the world where this system doesn't exist or doesn't work properly. In these areas, the safety of citizens in the event of an accident or illness is not guaranteed. Lack of medical equipment, long distances between hospitals or low qualifications of emergency workers cause that assistance provided to the casualty is low quality and usually is limited to transport.

The interest in Emergency Medical Care in Ghana began in 2001 when a construction disaster occurred at a sports stadium. At this time 126 people died. The Ghana National Ambulance Service was created in 2004, and then in 2009 a three-year specialization in emergency medicine for physicians and a specialization for nurses was opened. It was the second country in sub-Saharan Africa which has managed to do so [1].

Life-saving services offered by Emergency Medical Care in Ghana are free. The use of these services in life-threatening situations is not common. A survey conducted in Accra from June to August 2013 shows that 43.8% of people know an emergency telephone number but 78.0% say that in life-threatening situations the patient's transportation using a taxi is faster than waiting for an ambulance [2]. For this reason, the majority of victims of accidents and illnesses reach the hospital by private means of transport. Improper way of evacuation and transport can cause the spinal cord injuries. 63% of the casualties die, of which up to 81% of deaths occur before the patient is taken to hospital [3]. Some of these cases are the result of a lack of trust to the proper functioning of emergency medical services and a lack of awareness of the hazards of improper evacuation and transport.

Despite major changes in recent years, Ghana does not have an effective medical rescue system. National Ambulance Service, created 12-month training programme for their employees. It includes 9 months of theoretical classes, 6 weeks of practice in hospital and 6

weeks of practice in ambulance service. [4]. However, these are only trainings for Ghana National Ambulance Service employees, which is a state medical emergency service. Other, private organizations have no designed training system and, due to lack of regulation, have no imposed recruitment requirements for the qualifications of medical rescue workers. However, all these individuals have the same right to provide medical emergencies as the National Ambulance Service. This results in a decrease of the quality of health services provided to the public.

Based on data from Ghana Ministry of Health, in 2015 Ghana had only 128 ambulances [5], as many as it was at the same time in the Małopolskie voivodship. The number of ambulances per 100,000 inhabitants is between 0.23 and 0.63 in each region [6] This is 10 times lower average than in Poland, where in 2014 the indicator for particular voivodships was between 3.3 and 5.2 ambulances per 100 000 inhabitants [7]. Ambulances are distributed based on demographic factors. In sparsely populated areas the distance between stations is very long.

According to the general definition of the Golden Hour in Emergency Medicine, a traumatic patient should be admitted to a hospital in 60 minutes after an accident, should be brought out of shock, should get the specialist medical care in the hospital and if required to get to the surgery room [8]. In Ghana ambulance response times are very long. Only 59.4% of the areas were accessible to the ambulance in 60 minutes, and after analyzing the location of the rescue station, only 79% of the population had access to the ambulance in 60 minutes. [6]. In most cases, an hour is only sufficient for commuting but the same time also counts for the transport of the patient to the hospital, as well as the time for assessment and management of the patient on the scene. A long wait for professional medical services can lead to worsening of health status and death. The situation is worse because of lack of first aid knowledge in the community. That is why the relationship between the response time of emergency medical teams and the effectiveness of rescue operations is one of the most important factors affecting the survival of accident victims [9].

Long distances between hospitals, as well as poor equipment, create further problems. Due to equipment deficits and specialists deficits, 30% of Ghana's population has no access to life-saving surgical procedures [10]. The reason for this is not only the long distance between hospitals but also the lack of ambulance supplies, the lack of adequate equipment in more closely located units and the lack of appropriately trained personnel to carry out surgical procedures. In life-threatening situations requiring spe-

cialist medical attention, long-distance transport is sometimes essential. Defective sanitary vehicles often limit the possibilities of transport.

The survival chain is as strong as its weakest link [4]. In Ghana even first aid rules are not widespread and population's skills and awareness are negligible. First aid courses and trainings in Ghana are rare and are provided mainly in large cities. There is no compulsory first aid training at any stage of education or beyond. When cardiac arrest begins, basic life-saving procedures (BLS) are key to maintaining the vital signs until the medical staff arrives. The use of early defibrillation in the pre-hospital care is impossible because ambulances do not have any defibrillators. Rescue departments are also poorly equipped and staff skills to respond to cardiac arrest are often limited. Low quality of hospital care has a negative impact on the patient's prognosis.

Conclusion:

An analysis of the epidemiological situation, statistics on resources and the condition of Emergency Medical Care system in Ghana indicates that due to the long distances between hospitals and long response times of ambulances, the first link in the survival chain needs to be strengthened by promoting community knowledge about Basic Life Support. Attention should also be paid to the need of increasing diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities in pre-hospital care. It is recommended to create a training adapted to the conditions in Ghana, primarily targeted at the reduction of pre-hospital death rates. The training should be available to all emergency medical units. Appropriately trained staff should be able to perform a physical examination even without equipment, should provide initial diagnosis and appropriate patient management to improve patient's prognosis by appropriate positions and maneuvers. Increasing of public knowledge on first aid and the qualification of medical workers could increase the survivability of traffic accidents' victims in pre-hospital care.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.